

IMPROVING ECONOMIC, ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE INSURANCE MARKET IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article identifies current trends in insurance and the factors that lead to the growth of the insurance market. Comparing the insurance market of Uzbekistan with the market of other countries, its shortcomings were identified and the results obtained show the development of the insurance market, as well as the improvement of services provided.

Keywords: insurance, insurance service, insurance market, insurance premium insurance product, solvency, level of capitalization, infrastructure, reinsurance.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ, ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННЫХ И ПРАВОВЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ РАЗВИТИЯ СТРАХОВОГО РЫНКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА

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Аннотация: В данной статье определены современные тенденции в страховании и факторы, которые приводят к росту страхового рынка. При сравнении страхового рынка Узбекистана с рынком других стран были выявлены его недостатки и полученные результаты свидетельствуют о развитии страхового рынка, а также совершенствовании предоставляемых услуг.

Ключевые слова: страхование, страховая услуга, страховой рынок, страховая премия, страховой продукт, платежеспособность, уровень капитализации, инфраструктура, перестрахование.

O'ZBEKISTONDA SUG'URTA BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY, TASHKILIIY VA HUQUQIY MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada sug'urtaning hozirgi tendentsiyalari va sug'urta bozorining o'sishiga olib keladigan omillar aniqlangan. O'zbekiston sug'urta bozorini boshqa davlatlar bozori bilan solishtirganda, uning kamchiliklari aniqlanib, olingan natijalar sug'urta bozorining rivojlanishi hamda ko'rsatilayotgan xizmatlar yaxshilanganidan dalolat beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: sug'urta, sug'urta xizmati, sug'urta bozori, sug'urta mukofoti sug'urta mahsuloti, to'lov qobiliyati, kapitallashuv darajasi, infratuzilma, qayta sug'urtalash.

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Introduction

Analysis of the factors influencing the development of the insurance system in the context of globalization shows that strengthening financial relations with large insurance companies, taking into account the specifics of our country, requires the use of modern management and insurance strategies and information services in managing services.

In the current situation, the scientific and theoretical basis of insurance services management is rapidly changing in the process of formation of the economy based on the factors and knowledge that affect it. In particular, each insured entity of the national economy operates under the influence of internal and external competition. Also, under the influence of innovations in the world, there is a growing need to introduce a new type of innovative services based on new knowledge in production.

The innovations of the insured in production are causing unpredictable changes in the behavior of buyers. In particular, such changes are service-specific. In particular, there is a need to move from public insurance services to individual insurance services.

Literature review

Foreign scientists have in-depth research experience in this area. The peculiarities of the state regulation of the insurance market and insurance premiums have been considered in the works of foreign scientists J. Keynes, J. Stigler, J. Gelbright, K. Meyer, François Quilbolt, William F. Sharp, Michel Badock and others.

The fact that economists are divided on the issue of organizing insurance services also indicates that this problem is not fully resolved [1-3].

Economist K.Kulshoshev "Insurance market is an objective economic law, a mechanism that connects buyers of insurance goods (insured, other stakeholders, especially the state), sellers of insurance goods (insurers, reinsurers) and meets the needs of both parties to the maximum" [4].

In the research work of A.M. Godin, the role of the insurance market in the financial system, as well as providing insurance protection to various financial institutions, insurance companies become one of the major players in the financial market through their investment activities and potential [5].

The main part

It is necessary to develop an insurance plan to ensure the commonality of all activities and goals in the insurance service business. This plan serves to effectively allocate all available resources, including time and funds, in making insurance service decisions.

Economic factors influence the development of insurance services, including the unemployment rate, inflation rate, real income of the consumer, access to credit, its interest rate and types. It is also affected by the prices of substitute goods, petroleum products, recreational equipment.

Insurance is a system of economic relations related to the payment of damages and other monetary compensation for damage caused by natural disasters, various accidents. The prospects for the development of insurance are inextricably linked with economic reform. The influence of the state in insurance relations is very large. The state itself organizes and takes control of insurance relations. However, the role of these services in the financial market of our country is not large yet. In developed countries, this system is more developed, with insurance premiums in GDP averaging 8-12 percent of GDP (Table 1). The share of this sector in the GDP of Uzbekistan is only 0.4%.

Table 1. The share of insurance in GDP in some countries

#	Countries	Share of GDP
1	South Korea	11 %
2	Germany	6 %
3	Russia	1,5%
4	Uzbekistan	0,4 %

Currently, there are about 40 insurers in the insurance market of Uzbekistan.

Most of the works of the above authors focus on macroeconomic problems and do not have enough information about the regional aspects of the development of the insurance market. The problem of activating the innovative and investment activities of insurance companies in the market also requires additional research.

In developed countries, any innovative investment project is not accepted without an insurance guarantee. Therefore, in our country, insurance plays a special role in the activities of any entity, stabilizes financial relations between them and should develop as an innovative service network in solving all the accumulated problems.

The main directions of reform and accelerated development of the insurance market of the Republic of Uzbekistan are as follows:

- Improving the regulatory framework in the field of insurance, including the consistent introduction of standards and recommendations of international organizations and best practices in this area;
- institutional development of the system of regulation of insurance activities aimed at ensuring the reliability and stability of the insurance market through the introduction of effective mechanisms of regulation and prudential supervision;
- increase the level of capitalization, solvency and financial stability of professional participants of the insurance market, improve the quality of their assets, as well as the development of investment activities of insurers;
- development and expansion of the insurance market infrastructure by activating the activities of insurance brokers, improving the system of insurance agents, the introduction of bank insurance mechanisms, as well as increasing the role of professional participants in the insurance market in general;
- strengthening the protection of the rights of consumers of insurance services and other subjects of insurance activity, increasing insurance literacy and public confidence in insurance, ensuring openness and transparency of the insurance market;
- expansion of the volume, type and quality of insurance services provided through the introduction of new innovative insurance products and the development of traditional products in high demand;
- extensive use of modern information technologies in the field of organization and regulation of insurance activities, active introduction and development of electronic types of insurance services;
- Improving the system of training, retraining and advanced training of insurance market specialists, the use of modern methods of education in the field of insurance, the promotion of research activities;
- formation and maintenance of a positive image of the national insurance market and increase its investment

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attractiveness, including through the integration of the national insurance market with international and foreign insurance markets [6].

Economic and legal regulation of insurance relations means the regulation of insurance market participants' activities employing market tools. On January 17, 2019 the Decree PF-5635 adopted the State Program on implementation of the Strategy of Action for the five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the "Year of active investments and social development" for 2017-2021. measures for the development of the average market. According to this program, the main objective of the development of the insurance market of Uzbekistan is to increase the level of insurance protection of property interests of individuals and legal entities, ensuring the effective functioning of the insurance market, taking into account international experience, and using modern market infrastructure. formation of effective market mechanisms for attraction of investment resources to the national economy. The key factor for the successful development of the national insurance system is the formation of a modern market infrastructure. In this regard, the insurance company needs to perform financial engineering of business processes.

Business processes methodology of insurance organizations perform the following tasks:

- Strategy Provides strategic planning of activities that must identify promising areas for insurance company development;

- Creation of organizational structure allowing optimization of activity of insurance company and its structural subdivisions;

- There is an opportunity to have operational control at all stages of the insurance company.

The purpose of reengineering is determined by the simplification of the organizational structure of the insurance organization, the redistribution and minimization of various resources, and the improvement of the quality of services in the rapidly changing national economy. Conducting business reinsurance in an insurance organization over some time, for example, changes the insurance organization every five years, taking into account external factors.

Business process reengineering is accomplished by modelling business processes using modern techniques and software. The most effective of the systematic analysis methodologies is SADT (Structured Analysis and Design Technique). The essence of this model is that at first the overall system is modelled and then divided into sections. First, the IDEF0 business process standard was adopted in the US and later used in other countries, for example, in the model IMF business processes. This model includes specific standards and provides an overview of the specifics of each standard insurance organization. IDEF0 includes business process modelling, DFD modelling and data processing. It is recommended to use modern business process tools in insurance organizations.

The scheme of business processes for dealing with legal entities in insurance companies is implemented as follows. The sales department is responsible for the sales process, the underwriting process is carried out in a separate section after the insurer completes the unified information system and underwrites the contract. Customer service and insurance claims are handled separately.

In such a business process one employee can provide all types of insurance to the client. When the client is offered insurance, a universal calculator connected to the corporate system is used and an automated paperwork model is used, which results in the reduction of customer requests. The underwriting department is responsible for the level of risk management and insurance portfolio risk, which will improve the quality of customer service and end conflicts between employees and departments.

Applying the above business model will allow the insurance organization to achieve the following:

1. Determines the main activities of the insurance organization.
2. Improve the business structure of the insurance organization and ensure its transparency.
3. It allows changing economic results in the intermediate stages, thus ensuring the implementation of strategic plans of the organization.
4. Reduction of expenses for the insurance business by the insurance organization.
5. Opportunistic costs are reduced, these costs can be at each stage of the business process and harm the intended business processes.

The quality of insurance services means the complex condition of the services provided, compliance with applicable technical standards, full compliance with individual or general requirements, compliance with national and international standards [7]. The quality of service will be high, medium, low, according to consumer demand.

President Sh. Mirziyoyev held a meeting on the development of the insurance services market on July 10 and proposed the establishment of an insurance market development agency.

One of the main reasons for this is that insurance services are not attractive enough. For example, in the last six months, the insurance industry collected 887 billion soums of insurance premiums, but the amount of insurance coverage paid to customers during this period amounted to only 11% of the premiums. In the world, this figure is on average 50-60%.

The need to radically reform the State Inspectorate for Insurance Supervision was discussed at a meeting under the Ministry of Finance.

➤ The industry needs not a supervisor, but a structure that introduces advanced and modern

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standards, creates a truly competitive environment among all participants and develops the insurance market, - said Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

It was proposed to establish the Insurance Market Development Agency and abolish the State Inspectorate for Insurance Supervision. The task is to develop a strategy for medium and long-term development of the insurance industry, to increase the amount of insurance premiums per capita by 3 times and the share of the industry in GDP by 2 times by 2022.

Insurance is needed in our most difficult situations, but the majority of the population does not trust this system and does not even have a basic knowledge about it. First of all, it is necessary to increase the confidence of the population and entrepreneurs in insurance. The Ministry of Finance and the Antimonopoly Committee were instructed to reduce the time and documents for consideration of insurance claims, to introduce a system of fair assessment of the insured event and prompt payment of payments.

Tasks were given to expand the mechanisms to support the investment activities of insurance companies. In particular, the tasks of encouraging insurance companies to engage in leasing activities and improving the system of taxation of leasing services have been identified.

It was noted that it is important to cover the economy with insurance services. The Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Investment and Foreign Trade were instructed to introduce mechanisms for state subsidies for part of the cost of insurance of agricultural exports.

Specific tasks have also been set to ensure the access of national insurance companies to international financial markets, to obtain international ratings through the introduction of advanced corporate governance.

Attention was also paid to the training of modern personnel in the field of insurance, training of specialists in prestigious foreign universities and advanced training in leading companies.

Speaking about the introduction of compulsory health insurance in Uzbekistan, the head of state stressed the need to carefully prepare for it, to form a minimum social package of medical services.

The main factors that negatively affect the insurance market are the economic environment in the country, as well as the purchasing power of the population and the volume of lending. However, the heads of insurance companies expect an increase in fees for adjusting tariffs for compulsory motor liability insurance, which will be one of the few drivers due to growth in the insurance industry [8].

According to insurance companies, in the first quarter of 2020 503.1 bln. soums of insurance premiums were collected. The total authorized capital of insurers is 782.4 billion soums. soums (138%). The volume of investments in the economy amounted to 2.834 trillion soums. He made up the sum. Of this, 55% is in bank deposits, 30% in shares, and the rest in other securities. There is a disproportion in the components of the insurance market in our country, ie 82% of voluntary insurance and 18% of compulsory insurance. In other developed countries, the share of compulsory insurance is 50%. One of the main solutions to the problem is the privatization proposal of insurance companies. This allows you to promote, attract as a way to manage insurance risks. Foreign investment and technology, the creation of new skilled workers, as well as the population will have more opportunities to choose insurance products, and competition with state insurance companies will increase.

Another trend in the global market is the introduction of a risk-based approach. Insurance companies not only assess the risks associated with premiums and liabilities, but also have the ability to assess assets, loans, and market risks [9]. This will allow for more active management of insurance capital. To attract foreign investors, this trend is spreading to emerging markets as well. In terms of capital management, a risk-based approach makes it more understandable and more comparable.

Increasing the volume of insurance premiums remains an important issue for developing countries, including Uzbekistan. By raising the insurance culture and explaining to the population that insurance is protection, we will reduce the burden on the state and increase the responsibility of companies for their obligations. In developed countries, 70% of the population is financially literate, compared to less than 30% in developing countries. This will allow developing the insurance industry in Uzbekistan in the future. People need to understand why they need to buy an insurance policy. Many people think that this is a waste of money. In addition, the level of consumer protection in Uzbekistan is very low. If consumers feel they are protected, they will also be willing to buy more insurance policies.

The general trend towards reducing staff costs and agency fees is fully consistent with insurers' desire to trade online [10].

Conclusion

In order to develop insurance services and ensure the use of insurance services by as many legal entities and individuals as possible, it is necessary to create a legal framework that covers all aspects of the industry. In addition, there is a lot of work to be done in the field of insurance services. Therefore, it is important to develop the process of mutual insurance through modern innovative approaches, the establishment of a system of non-profit mutual insurance society in

our country and the development of its legal framework. Such a company must serve to insure the property and other property interests of its members.

The development of the insurance services market will allow to achieve high rates of socio- economic development and a positive solution to social problems in the country, the effective use of productive forces and means.

In short, the insurance service sector, which is one of the key sectors of the financial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, should take full advantage of the potential of our country today and learn more about the laws of the world's major insurance markets. should apply.

In short, in order to increase operational efficiency, it is necessary to review and improve the organizational structure of organizations, ie the widespread introduction of digitalization in insurance activities. Another important aspect is the need to establish a mechanism of constant communication with customers in order to develop and ensure the effectiveness of modern insurance products in order to take a worthy place in the insurance market, strengthen financial stability and competitiveness. Along with improving the quality of insurance services, one of the important tasks is to increase the share of the industry in GDP and protect the economy from various financial risks.

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